

INNOVATIVE PROCESSES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article reveals the features of the innovative process at the university, ensuring the use and dissemination of innovations in the educational process. Particular attention is paid to: 1) the stages of the innovative process; 2) the division of innovations by features; 3) the use of algorithmic technologies; 4) the role of humanization and humanitarization of the educational process at the university. The essence and principle of humanitarization of the educational process are revealed, taking into account the integral system of humanitarian education.*

Keywords: *educational innovation; innovation; innovative process; humanization; humanitarization; innovation system; activity-based approach.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern society is in a state of continuous development and change. The education system in such a society must also change and improve in order to meet the demands of society and the state. And one of these methods, the ability of the education system to respond to the challenges of the time, is introduction of *innovation*, qualitatively new aspect, into the established education system.

The need for students to assimilate a large amount of information and develop practical skills for its application leads to the creation by teachers of new ways of presenting information, new technologies and methods of teaching, forces them to look for creative approaches to teaching methods.

Innovation is the introduction of new methodologies and standards into the process. Obedience, repetition, imitation are replaced by new requirements: the ability to see problems, calmly accept them, and solve them independently.

Innovative education involves learning in the process of creating new knowledge - through the integration of fundamental science, the educational process itself and production. It brings with it new foundations for developing education, as the main modernizing factor of education. In relation to the pedagogical process, innovation means introducing something new into the goals, content, methods and forms of teaching and education, organizing the joint activities of the teacher and the student.

The goal of innovative activity is a qualitative change in student's personality in comparison with the traditional system. This becomes possible due to the introduction of unknown didactic and educational programs into professional activity, which involves the removal of the pedagogical crisis. Developing the ability to motivate actions, independently navigate the information received, and forming creative, unconventional thinking are the main goals of innovative activity.

Innovative activity in education as a socially significant practice aimed at the moral self-improvement of a person is important in that it is capable of ensuring the transformation of all existing types of practices in society.

Educational innovation is an innovation in professional activity, changes in the content and technology of teaching and upbringing students, ensuring their effectiveness. The innovation process is the use and dissemination of innovations. Innovation is a means (new method, methodology, technology, program, etc.), and innovation is the process of mastering this means.

The innovative process is based on three main stages: 1) generating an idea (sometimes a scientific discovery); 2) developing an idea in an applied aspect; 3) implementing the innovation in practice.

The innovativeness of a teacher can be considered as:

- personal characteristics;
- an activity during which a student, a future specialist, transforms himself as a future professional;
- the process of knowing oneself, one's creative potential, revealing one's own abilities;
- search for solutions to problems and pedagogical tasks;
- the process of professional and personal self-expression;
- the process of developing professional thinking.

Existing innovations are divided (depending on the feature): 1) by type of activity: pedagogical, managerial; 2) by the nature of the changes introduced (radical - based on new ideas, combinatorial - on a combination of known, modifying on the improvement of existing); 3) by the scale of the changes introduced; 4) by the problematics; 5) by the area of implementation: in content, in structure, in technologies; 6) by the source of occurrence: external, internal; 7) by the scale of use: single, diffuse; 8) by functional capabilities; 9) by the scale of socio-pedagogical significance (international, regional, for an educational institution); 10) by the intensity of innovative change or the level of innovativeness; 11) by comprehension before the implementation of innovations: random, useful, systemic.

In a traditional educational environment, the potential for individualization of the educational process is limited by the capabilities of one teacher conducting the lesson. The use of information technologies allows for the maximum individualization of the educational process, building it taking into account the characteristics of a specific student, ensuring his active, activity-based work on self-development.

To create and operate an innovative educational environment based on information technology, it is necessary to implement several areas: software and hardware, organizational and methodological; psychological and pedagogical; creative and developmental.

The software and hardware direction includes equipping the university with modern multimedia computers, creating computer training programs in various disciplines, educational videos, and materials for independent study.

The technological and methodological direction includes the development of various types of educational activities in a creative form (lectures, practical and laboratory work, business games, seminars and conferences) using a computer, multi-projector, visual and sound effects, video and animation, various educational programs, testing systems, digital technologies.

Psychological and pedagogical direction includes the development of basic methodological approaches, models, pedagogical conditions, goals and objectives of the functioning of the innovative educational environment, its structure and content.

The organizational and managerial direction includes the organization of activities to create an innovative educational environment and the management of its functioning.

Creative and developmental direction includes the creation of conditions in the innovative educational environment of the university that promote the creative development of student's personality, the development and implementation in educational and extracurricular activities of techniques, forms and methods for developing the creative abilities of students using information technologies.

Education using this technology ceases to be only a learning activity taking place in educational institutions, in specially organized conditions, but becomes a mandatory process in any productive activity, occurring throughout the entire active life of the individual, thereby acting as a form of continuous education of the individual.

It is more correct to call such education projective not only because a project is used as a teaching method, but most importantly because the teaching itself is a means of creating and implementing a project that has a vital, and not just educational, meaning for the student. Unlike mass education, it becomes personalized.

An innovative approach to teaching or education means the introduction and use of innovations in the educational process of an educational institution. An innovative system is a system operating in an innovative mode, in which experimental research work is actively conducted or created. Innovations are implemented and used in certain components.

The solution to the problem of creating new generation of educational technologies is seen in the path of integrating a number of existing educational technologies (ICT). To solve the problem, it is possible to use the following algorithmic technologies: programmed learning, full assimilation technology, modular learning technology, educational cycle technology, integrated technology, cognitive technology, activity-based approach technology, etc.

A significant role in refraction of the growing negative trends in the educational sphere in our country is given to the principles of humanization and humanitarization of education proclaimed in the early 90s of the twentieth century. When speaking about humanitarization of education, they mean only an increase in the share of humanities in the curricula of the university. At the same time, students are offered various art history and other humanities disciplines, which are rarely directly related to the future activities of a specialist, but this is the so-called "external humanitarization". Among the scientific and technical intelligentsia, a technocratic style of thinking prevails, which students "absorb " from the very beginning of their studies at the university. Therefore, they treat the study of humanities as something secondary, sometimes demonstrating outright nihilism.

The essence of humanization of education lies primarily in the formation of a culture of thinking, creative abilities of the student based on a deep understanding of psychology and pedagogy, the history of culture and civilization, the entire cultural heritage. The university is called upon to prepare a specialist capable of constant self-development, self-improvement, and the richer the student's nature, the brighter it will manifest itself in professional activity.

The principle of humanitarization of innovative education means, firstly, identifying the humanitarian potential of disciplines, allowing us to speak of them as part of human culture. Secondly, it is reflected in the content of education, forming a holistic idea of the scientific picture of the world. Thirdly, the principle is implemented in teaching methods that allow us to form the experience of mental, search, creative, labor and other activities of students, the experience of their emotional and value relationships, etc.

An integrated system of humanitarian education should conditionally include knowledge divided into three groups (spheres): knowledge of an individual about himself and his peers; knowledge of the social environment in which he is included; knowledge of the external world (living and inanimate nature), in which societies of individuals are located. Each of these spheres requires a special set of subjects and a special methodology.

To organize educational innovation, it is necessary to identify levels of knowledge acquisition and methods of activity: the first level means readiness to reproduce, consciously perceive and record knowledge in memory; the second level is readiness to apply knowledge according to a model, and the third level is readiness (based on generalization and systematization of what has been learned) to apply knowledge in a non-standard situation. The development of cognitive activity is also facilitated by non-traditional lessons, which increase the student's interest in the subject and in learning in general. There are several classifications of non-standard lessons and many of their types: lesson-seminar, lesson-lecture, lesson-conversation, lesson-workshop, lesson-excursion, lesson-research, lesson-game, lesson-KVN, lesson-project defense, lesson-dispute, lesson-conference, lesson-theatrical performance, lesson-masquerade, lesson-journey,

lesson-test. Almost all of them allow you to ask problem questions and create problem situations, solve the problems of differentiated learning, intensify educational activities, increase cognitive interest, and contribute to the development of critical thinking. Non-traditional lessons of Russian language and literature provide a systematic analysis of linguistic information, develop linguistic observation. Theory and practice show that the significant potential for professional and personal growth of participants in the pedagogical process lies in the use of innovative educational technologies. As evidenced by the historical analysis of the category of "pedagogical technology", it can be based on three educational strategies: rationalistic (technocratic), developing, personality-oriented. The study of their essence allows us to single out the following parameters for comparison: the values of pedagogical activity, the nature of pedagogical influence, taking into account personal and individual characteristics, the position of the teacher and the student in the educational process, its result, the presence of a reflective component in the activity. Changes in the goal and essence of education within the framework of a personality-oriented paradigm allows us to speak about the emergence of a new category of "educational technology", which is based on the understanding of the educational process as a self-developing system, where the student's activity becomes the leading factor, and learning acts as reflexive control, which presupposes intersubjective interaction of the teacher and the student and ensuring the development of their capabilities. Educational technology appears in the research as personality-oriented and, according to the main essential features of innovation, it can be defined as innovative.

The analysis of practice shows that the development of innovative educational technologies is impeded by the lack of formation of the corresponding teacher's activity. The innovative process as a process of development, assimilation, use of innovations in mass practice for these technologies ends at the stage of development or experimental verification, and the absence of a stage of "wide" implementation does not allow us to speak about the completeness of the innovation. Despite the existing developments in the field of pedagogical technologies, management of the development of innovative processes, the issue of implementation, that is, the use of innovative educational technologies in mass practice remains insufficiently developed. Thus, it is necessary to resolve the contradiction: between the objective need for the implementation of innovative educational technologies and the teacher's unwillingness to use

them, as well as the lack of theoretical substantiation of the pedagogical conditions of the teacher's activity in the implementation of innovative educational technologies. This contradiction constitutes a research problem. The urgency of the problem and its practical significance determined the choice of the research topic: "The teacher's activity in the implementation of innovative educational technologies." In accordance with the goal, problem, object and subject of the study, the following tasks were set: to determine methodological approaches to the study of the problem of implementation of innovative educational technologies; to identify the essence of innovative educational technologies; reveal the structure of the teacher's activities in the implementation of innovative educational technologies; develop indicators of the teacher's readiness for their implementation; to reveal the pedagogical conditions of the teacher's activity in the implementation of innovative educational technologies; develop and experimentally test a program for the formation of teacher's activities for the implementation of innovative educational technologies.

As a hypothesis of the study, it was suggested that the success of a teacher in the implementation of innovative educational technologies is determined by professional and personal readiness, which is formed in innovative activities and is ensured by the following conditions:

- the inclusion of teachers in the process of intersubjective dialogue interaction;
- teaching teachers generalized skills: design and skills to manage self-directed learning activities of students;
- the development of the ability to identify opportunities for self-improvement through intellectual and personal reflection.

CONCLUSION

Active mastering of innovative education, its effective application imply not only the development and integration of skills and abilities, the development of individual methods and techniques for performing professional work, but also mastering the methodology of professional creativity, the development of creative thinking and the necessary creative personal qualities. The formation of a creative personality can be defined as the formation and development of a personality adequate to the creative activity performed and the creative results obtained. The pace and trajectory of this process are determined by biological and social factors, the individual's own activity and creative qualities, as well as circumstances, vital events and professionally determined factors. A close relationship arises between the formation of a creative personality and innovative education [3]. Therefore, innovative education is beginning to occupy an increasingly significant position in the system of human sciences. Hence the dependence of the levels of professional and creative activity of a person, the results achieved and the levels of his innovative training as readiness to implement and achieve them. As a result, we see that all the problems of general and professional education are united around the integral process of professional development of a creative personality. At the same time, the expediency of integrating these problems into one branch of pedagogy - innovative pedagogy - is obvious.

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